

Industry-Community-University-Finance Collaboration scheme for Project Based-Learning of Engineering Education

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Abstract

The College of Systems Engineering and Science and the Systems Engineering and Science Course, Graduate School of Engineering and Science have been conducting an industry-community-university collaborative engineering educational program for about 20 years. However, the general attitude on the part of companies, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) which are the majority, in Japan has been that being difficult to approach and they have never considered about industry-community-university collaboration. This seemed to indicate that there might be something wrong with the general scheme of industry-community-university collaboration in Japan.

In this study, instead of using the company's business issues and new business development as research subjects, we introduced them as project subjects and developed a scheme for (1) planning based on system thinking, (2) demonstration experiments and prototyping, and (3) creating innovation by introducing diverse perspectives. A new industry-community-university collaboration scheme was constructed to draw out new business and research elements from the outcome obtained from PBL on this scheme, leading to commissioned and joint research. Using this scheme, the Special Exercises in Systems Engineering (SE2), the Cross-Innovation Project (CIP) and the Cross-cultural Engineering Project (CEP) were performed on PBL. In FY2024, 30 projects were executed in SE2 and in CIP, 13 projects, including one entrepreneurship project, were executed including 10 projects that were continued from SE2 in CIP. To create innovation through diversity and the introduction of new perspectives, CEP@Portugal (FCT NOVA and University of Minho, Portugal) was combined for SE2 projects and CEP@SIT for CIP projects. The scheme was verified and validated by outcomes of SE2, CIP and CEP using this scheme. The results obtained are presented in this paper.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning, Engineering education, System Thinking, Generic Skills, Innovation

1 Introduction

The Age of VUCA has long been recognized after various world affairs. In addition, with the digitalization, robotization, and democratization of AI in recent years, Joseph Aoun, President of Northeastern University, has suggested that Higher Education in the Age of AI requires education in systems thinking, critical thinking, entrepreneurship, and cross-cultural agility (Joseph, 2018).

Furthermore, to create new value, innovative creation is needed. The framework for innovative creation has changed dramatically from the old linear system that transferred science to technology and then deployed the outcome into business. And then, in an innovative ecosystem, technologies deployed from science are combined and transformed into business, and the returns from its commercialization are invested in the combination of technologies. Such an ecosystem has been required, however, now, the accelerating speed of research and development through AI, computing, and digitalization has brought science, technology, and business into close-proximity. Therefore, a strategic response is required, as shown in Figure 1, to develop frontier markets by investing not only in combination of technologies but also in the science of its advancement (METI, 2025). This strategic response is not a closed strategy to be carried out individually by the government, industry, universities, and financial institutions, but a collaborative process among these institutions based on

open innovation. The close-proximity of science, technology, and business (Figure 1) cannot be achieved with the old research and development scheme, thus requiring a change of a mindset in which science and technology research domain are crossed business domain, i.e., including business models. However, the realization of this close-proximity scheme is not easy.

Figure 1. Strategic response for development of frontier markets (METI, 2025).

On the other hand, the government suggests that this scheme requires the industry-community-university-finance collaboration based on open innovation for acceleration. With this background, each university is building an open innovation environment, and Shibaura Institute of Technology has launched the Bay area Open innovation Center (BOiCE) in Tokyo Bay area. It provides Open Laboratory Innovation, Open Learning Innovation, Open Social Innovation, Open Resource Innovation, and Open Field Innovation. Under this environment, universities in the science and technology (research institutions) are expected to contribute to society, and if the science and technology that acts as seeds match the needs of the business domain, collaboration is expected to advance.

However, this matching is difficult, and according to those working in the area of industry-academia-government collaboration, only about 10-20% of all academies they know are active in industry-academia-government collaboration (Maenami, 2013). In addition, large and global companies have MOUs with universities, while Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), which are the majority, have not progressed well as indicated by the mutual recognition between industry, academia, and government that hinders industry-academia collaboration (Nagata, 2006), and even now there is no significant difference. In addition, the matching of engineering education between universities and industries is matched as a whole but mismatched in a lot of threads (Wakabayashi, 2018).

In this study, instead of using the company's business issues and new business development as research subjects, we introduced them as project subjects and developed a scheme for (1) planning based on system thinking, (2) demonstration experiments and prototyping, and (3) creating innovation by introducing diverse perspectives. A new industry-community-university collaboration scheme was constructed to draw out new business and research elements from the outcome obtained from Project Based-Learning (PBL) on this scheme, leading to commissioned and joint research. This paper describes the development of industry-community-university-finance collaboration scheme as an engineering education-based scheme based on strategic responses for frontier market development in Chapter 2, case studies of PBL using the developed scheme in Chapter 3. and the findings obtained in Chapter 4.

2 Industry-Community-University-Finance Collaboration scheme

In order to realize a strategic response to the development of frontier markets (Figure 1), it is important to search for science and technology to quickly progressing from early stage to business and to match them with research institutions in that field. However, few researchers are collaborating with industry-academia, and there is actually a mismatch between the objectives of the company views and those of the academia views, as shown in Figure 2. This is thought to be a fundamental problem in that matching is performed for the specific objectives, i.e., specific solution, of both sides. Therefore, we have to solve this mismatch problem. If this problem is not solved, it cannot be considered to be a fundamental solution.

Figure 2. Conflicts between companies and academic researchers

2.1 From research-based strategy to engineering education-based strategy

For solving this fundamental problem, we reversed the strategic response scheme for the development of frontier markets based on the research (Figure 1) and developed a strategic response scheme based on engineering education, as shown in Figure 3, in which problem discovery based on multi-national and multidisciplinary PBL is carried out together with the business side. In this scheme, the project activities are conducted by multi-national and multidisciplinary members to identify problems with the business side's major objective as the problem. And the system planning that will be the solution is created by a mixture of science and engineering students considering cross-cultural agility, as shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3. From research-based strategy to engineering education-based strategy for change of a mindset in which science and technology research domain are crossed business domain

The knowledge and experience that will form the basis of this project activities are acquired based on the System thinking Engineering education program (SE education program) shown in Figure 4.

This SE education program starts with the Workshop of system-thinking and consists of lectures and exercises of Systems Engineering A and B, which are the required subject of the undergraduate school. And, in the graduate school, System Engineering, which lectures on entrepreneurship based on system thinking, and Special Exercise of Systems Engineering (SE2), which proposes system planning to solve real world problems, are required subject. The knowledge and experience obtained through this SE education program are developed into the culminating Cross Innovation Project (CIP) (Mochizuki, 2020) and Cross-cultural Engineering Project (CEP) (Navas, 2020, Kongwat, 2021, Hasegawa, 2023 & Otsuka, 2024). In CIP, demonstration experiments and prototyping based on the planning proposed in SE2 are conducted, and in CEP, a multicultural and multidisciplinary PBL, projects are brushed up from a cross-cultural agility and global viewpoint. In this way, knowledge and experience are consolidated as Generic Skills through step-by-step repetition of exercises and lectures.

Figure 4. System thinking Engineering (SE) education program

2.2 Development of collaboration scheme

The industry-community-university-finance collaboration scheme developed based on the concept of the engineering education-based strategy (Figure 3) is shown in Figure 5. This scheme is applied in SE2, CIP, and CEP, which are the culmination of the SE education program.

As shown in Figure 5, instead of matching university research seeds with management issues and new business development in industries and communities, a project exercise of SE2 is started with the problem finding and clarification of tasks through system thinking. In the SE2 project teams with a mixture of different disciplines, after clarifying tasks, the team members generate ideas and make proposals for system planning. At the time of system planning in these projects, innovative creation from different viewpoints will be conducted with EU

students at CEP@Portugal (FCT NOVA and University of Minho, Portugal) to brush up the system proposals, will be proposed as the final system planning.

In the following CIP, innovation and global viewpoints will be reflected in the project in the same way by crossing CIP and CEP@SIT with mixed overseas students. By taking these various perspectives into consideration in prototyping and demonstration experiments, attractive solutions will be derived.

New businesses and research elements are extracted from the project outcomes through this scheme and are transformed into new businesses and lead to commissioned joint multidisciplinary research.

Through the reversal approach described above, we will try to develop frontier markets for the creation of new value through business, science, and technology close-proximity.

Figure 5. The Industry-Community-University-Finance Collaboration scheme.

3 Case studies of PBL based on developed scheme

3.1 Consideration of number of the provided issue

We implemented a multidisciplinary type's PBL using the development scheme to solve problems based on the social needs of SMEs and local communities. Figure 6 shows the number of provided issue in FY2022 before the scheme was developed and the number of provided issue after the developed scheme was applied every year. The number of issues is shown for large and global companies (LGCs), SMEs, communities (COMMs), and financial institutions. In addition, as an entrepreneurship education, an entrepreneurship project (ENTRE PJ) was started in FY2023, which is a project with a theme that combines the leader's motivation and social contribution. The number of ENTRE PJs is also included in the figure.

First, the number of provided issues to SE2 (required subject) shows that many SMEs, which previously considered it difficult to provide issue for industry-university collaboration, have started to provide many issues. In addition, LGCs have started to apply the issues following the SMEs. There was no increase or decrease in the number of regional issues, depending on whether or not a developed scheme was introduced. On the other hand, financial institutions have changed their style from themes related to their own issues and events to providing issues of SMEs that they support. It is believed that this change in style is due to the fact that financial institutions are now considering that industry-university-finance collaboration can be used as a sales tool.

Next, CIP, is elective subject, was performed 12 projects including two entrepreneurship projects in FY2023. Nine of these projects were carried over from SE2. In FY2024, 30 projects were carried out in SE2 and 13 projects in CIP that consisted of one entrepreneurship project and 10 projects from SE2. Since CIP is an elective subject, the total number of provided issues remains unchanged.

Figure 6. Number of provided issue under the developed scheme. In FY2022, number of provided issue before the development of this scheme.

3.2 Case study of SE2 and CEP collaboration

As a case study of this scheme, the outline of the Nasu Area Innovation Project is described. This project is a tourism service called KANKO, which uses technology to realize the aroma of tourist attractions in Nasu Town, Tochigi Prefecture, where the emperor's official residence is located, so that tourists can visit the places where they can smell the aroma.

The refinement of the scent and this concept creation was completed by the second design review (DR2) in SE2, and how to realize the circulation process using the scent and the business model were conducted at CEP@Portugal (FCT NOVA) together with EU students. Based on outcomes of CEP@Portugal, project team proposed a system planning at the Final Presentation (FP) of SE2. A sustainable proposal was made to develop a capsule toy using scents extracted from Nasu's natural resources and wastes. A business model was proposed that would not only be enjoyed by tourists, but would also benefit the businesses in Nasu, and boost Nasu as a whole.

Figure 7. Case studies of SE2 and CEP collaboration: KANKO, Scenting Project.

This system planning was demonstrated in CIP in autumn semester. The scents were productized using wax art, and then the scent was based on the three themes of hot springs, nature, and coffee, which are Nasu's strengths, and a total of six tourist spots were proposed. A total of 240 capsule toys were prepared, and all 240 were distributed in two days. With the successful results of the project up to this stage, they participated in the 4th business competition sponsored by a company and won the third place. Based on this project outcome, they are planning to launch the first aroma business in July 2025, together with a company in Nasu Town.

3.3 Case study of CIP and CEP collaboration

This project is a shared mobility project for the realization of a secondary transportation system (Last one mile) for tourism areas. The shared mobility was conceptualized through the first and second design reviews of the CIP, and then, in CEP@SIT (multi-national and multidisciplinary PBL with industry-university collaboration held Shibaura Institute of Technology in Japan), they were visited in the target tourism spot, Nasu area, to brush up the use cases. And a 3D printer was made a scale model of the obtained conceptual design. After confirming the behaviours using this scale model and calculating the strength using CAE, a prototype was manufactured together with SMEs, and the manufactured prototype was exhibited at an exhibition hosted by Saitama Prefecture. Driving experiments using this prototype and detailed studies using multi-body dynamics simulations revealed the need for further improvements and design studies. This project activity was the launching for shared mobility research with SMEs.

CIP: Demonstration experiment and prototyping: Planning

CEP@SIT: Demonstration experiment and prototyping: Planning

Project outcomes: Prototype on exhibit

Figure 8. Case studies of CIP and CEP collaboration: Shared mobility project.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, a new scheme for industry-community-university-finance collaboration is developed. This scheme corresponds to a strategic response to develop frontier markets. The strategic response is usually a research-based strategy, and industry-university collaboration schemes in the close-proximity of business and science and technology have various difficulties in matching research seeds and business needs.

To solve this difficulty, we applied reverse thinking and combined PBL with engineering education to devise an engineering education-based on strategy. Based on this strategic response, an industry-community-university-finance collaboration scheme was developed. By using the developed scheme, the following outcomes were confirmed:

- The number of provided issues by SMEs increased drastically compared to when the scheme was not adopted. In FY2025, there were some cases where companies that wanted to offer provided issue was rejected.
- The scheme indicated that it is possible to find problems, conduct demonstration experiments, and make them into businesses through the implementation of project activities.
- In the same way, the need to start with project activities, develop prototyping, and then improve and explore new designs occurred, leading to joint research with SMEs.

In the future, more robust empirical data, such as measurable educational and business outcomes, and comparative analysis with traditional university-industry collaboration models will be conducted to clarify the effectiveness of this scheme.

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